

Synthesis and Spectral Studies on Mono- and Trialkyltin(IV) and Triphenyltin(IV) Chelates with Substituted-8-quinolinols†

(Misa) C. D. BARSODE, P. UMAPATHY* and D. N. SEN

National Chemical Laboratory, Poona-8

Manuscript received 19 November 1976, revised 26 April 1977, accepted 13 July 1977

Several mono- and trialkyl/triphenyltin(IV)-substituted-8-quinolinols have been synthesised and characterised by their elemental analysis, U. V. and I. R. spectral data. The absorption bands located at Ca. 570 cm^{-1} , 440 cm^{-1} and at Ca. 360 cm^{-1} in the alkyltin(IV) chelates have been assigned to the tin-carbon, tin-oxygen and tin-nitrogen stretching frequencies respectively. The U. V. spectra of these compounds show the presence of chelating oxine groups.

A few mixed chelates of the type $R_2SnL_1L_2$ (where $HL_1=8$ -quinolinol and $HL_2=$ a β -diketone, dibenzoylmethane or benzoylacetone) also have been isolated and characterised.

THE ability of organotin moieties to react with potentially chelating ligands to form stable complexes with high coordination is well established. The 8-quinolinol derivatives are classical examples of 5-, 6- and 7-coordinate chelates reported in literature¹⁻⁵. Although most of the conventional techniques namely Mössbauer, I.R. and N.M.R. spectroscopies have been employed as aids in structural investigations,^{1,2,6} the geometry of certain of these oxinates is still in doubt. Triphenyltin oxinate has been studied by several investigators and from its U.V. spectral data, in 95% methanol, it was concluded that $R_3S_2^+$ cations could not form a chelate⁷. However, Okawara and coworkers⁸ have found that in anhydrous cyclohexane, triphenyltin oxinate is, indeed, chelated and tin is penta-coordinated. Among the seven-coordinate organotin chelates, mention may be made of phenyltin tristropolonate⁹ and butyltintrisoxinate. In continuation of our studies on dialkyltin(IV) substituted-8-quinolinols,^{10,11} several stable complexes of mono- and trialkyltin(IV) substituted-8-quinolinols have been synthesised. In addition, dialkyltin(IV) mixed chelates of the type $R_2SnL_1L_2$ ($HL_1=8$ -quinolinol and $HL_2=$ a β -diketone) and chloroorganotin chelates, $RSnClOx$, ($HOx=5,7$ -disubstituted-8-quinolinol) have been isolated in pure state. The salient features of the U. V. spectra of these compounds along with dialkyltin(IV)bis-substituted-8-quinolinolates, the I. R., P.M.R. and mass spectral data for some of the organotin(IV) chelates are presented in this paper.

Experimental

The U.V. spectra of all the tin(IV) chelates were recorded (in different solvents) on an Unicam SP 500 spectrophotometer. The I.R. spectra in Nujol mull were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer model 221 spectrophotometer. The P. M. R. spectra were recorded

on a Varian T-60 spectrometer operating at 60 MC/s with TMS as internal standard. The mass spectra of the mixed chelates were recorded on CEC-21-110B (USA) Double focussing spectrometer at voltage of 70 eV and a current of 20 milliamperes.

Triethyltinchloride and ethyltin trichloride were prepared according to the methods described by Luijten and Vander Kerk^{12,13}. Triphenyltin chloride is a gift sample and is used as such.

The trisligand complexes were prepared by following a general procedure : To a solution of ethyltintrichloride (0.6 g., 0.0025 mole) in alcohol (10 ml.), the ligand (0.0075 mole) in alcohol (30 ml.) was added with vigorous stirring. Stirring was continued for 15 mts. and the pH of the solution was adjusted to ~5.5 with alcoholic sodium acetate solution. The precipitates obtained were collected on a filter, dried under vacuum and were further purified by recrystallization from solvents mentioned in Table 1. The triaryl or alkyl tin(IV) chelates were also obtained in a similar manner. The syntheses of dialkyltin(IV) chelates were described elsewhere^{10,11}.

Mixed chelates : Diethyltin(IV) mixed chelates have been synthesised directly by refluxing diethyltin dichloride, 8-quinolinol and a β -diketone (dibenzoylmethane or benzoylacetone) in a solvent (alcohol) for 5-6 hrs. and by adjusting the pH of the mixed solutions to ~5.5. The isolated solids were further purified by several recrystallisations. The physical and analytical data for the organotin(IV)-substituted oxinates are presented in Tables 1-4.

† N. C. L. Communication No. 2092

* Author to whom correspondence should be addressed.

Results and Discussion

U. V. Spectra : The bands of 8-hydroxyquinolinolate anion have been assigned by several workers¹⁴⁻¹⁷ and according to these authors the absorption band appearing at 322 nm is the low energy transition, 1L_a and the one at 317.5 nm is the high energy transition, 1L_b . In the U.V. spectra of alkyltin(IV) substituted oxinates R_3SnL , R_2SnL_2 , $RSnCl(L)_2$ and $RSnL_3$ (where L=anion of a substituted oxine) two well separated bands at relatively low energy, one in the region 360-400 nm and another at Ca. 340 nm. are observed. From the position and intensity, the band at 360-400 nm is supposed to be the ligand band strongly shifted from its original position (1L_a). The other band at Ca.340 nm is in the same position as the usual 1L_b band and is found to be insensitive to changes in substituent or solvent. The shift to longer wave length of 320 nm. absorption band suggests that, in solution, the organotin compounds listed in Table 2 contain a chelated(substituted oxinato)ligand.^{14-16,18,19} The other band which is weak in compounds 8 and 15 but intense in 1 to 7, 9 to 14 and 16 to 21 is also observed in the spectra of other metal oxinates.¹⁶⁻¹⁸

The chelates with formula R_3SnL form a new class of compounds containing a penta-coordinated tin atom and the chelates $RSnL_3$ are probably having trigonal bipyramidal configurations.^{3,21} There has been some disagreement concerning the structure of Ph_3SnOX and Ruddleick and Sams^{2,20} from their studies on ^{119}Sn Mössbauer spectra of organotin(IV) oxinates in applied magnetic fields have concluded that Ph_3SnOx is five coordinate.

The magnitude of the shift of 320 nm absorption band in the U. V. spectra of chelated oxinato complexes has been correlated with the complex stability^{16,22}. If the relation between the band shift and stability is applicable in these chelates the following sequence of stability in solvents, such as, cyclohexane, methanol can be obtained from the table 4.

It is observed that the shift of the ligand band to longer wave lengths is, in general, more in organotin substituted oxinates, compared to the shift reported for the corresponding organotin oxinates. The separation between 1L_a and 1L_b transitions of certain oxinato complexes has been used as a rough measure of the π bonding between cations and the ring, since the relative positions of the two transitions are insensitive to changes in σ bonding by cations²³.

Although the U. v. spectrum of $(C_2H_5)_2Sn$ (dibromo Ox) in cyclohexane indicates clearly the presence of chelated oxine ligand, in aqueous methanol, the 390 nm band is reduced in intensity and a strong band is observed at Ca.320 nm. This suggests that the Sn-N bond of triorganotin oxinates becomes weaker in polar solvents. The changes observed in methanol may be ascribed to solvolysis.^{22,24}

I. R. spectra : In the I. R. spectra of 5-, 7- and 5,7-disubstituted-8-quinolinols a broad, medium to weak intensity band at Ca.3200 cm^{-1} , which may be associated with an inter/intramolecularly bonded OH vibration, is observed. In the solution spectra of several substituted-8-quinolinols, Badger and Moritz²⁵ observed such a band at Ca.3400-3350 cm^{-1} . The medium intensity band present in the ligands at Ca.1410 cm^{-1} can be ascribed to the phenolic OH in plane deformation vibration coupled with C-O Str. mode. The second coupled mode expected at Ca. 1200 cm^{-1} could be located in all substituted-8-quinolinols. However, the OH out of plane deformation vibration at Ca.850 cm^{-1} could not be located clearly due to ligand absorptions. The C=N str. frequency somewhat coupled with pyridine ring vibration appears as a strong band in substituted-8-quinolinols at Ca.1580 cm^{-1} . In dialkyltin(IV) chelates and in mono- or triorganotin(IV) chelates, however, this band shifts²⁶ to Ca.1570 cm^{-1} and to 1560 cm^{-1} respectively. The characteristic²⁷

ν -o stretching frequency at C-O-M site is observed at

~ 1100 cm^{-1} in the spectra of all substituted-8-quinolinols. The bands observed at Ca.1280, 1190, 1150 cm^{-1} spectra of the compounds may be attributed to in the substituted pyridine ring vibrations²⁸.

In the spectra of organotin(IV) compounds except in the chelates of 5-nitro-7-bromo-8-quinolinol, strong bands characteristic of Sn-alkyl groups are observed which are not present in the spectra of the ligands. In diethyltin(IV) compounds particularly, the asymmetric CH_2 -deformation of Sn-Et can be located at Ca.1440 cm^{-1} . The symmetric mode, however, cannot be located precisely, since this region (~ 1180 cm^{-1}) is masked by ligand absorptions. In diethyltin dialkoxides and other dialkyltin dialkoxides, $Et_2Sn(OR)_2$, the asymmetric and symmetric CH_2 -deformation modes of Sn-Et are reported at 1456 cm^{-1} and at 1188 cm^{-1} respectively²⁹. Another new characteristic band observed in the spectra of organotin(IV) compounds is the CH_2 -Sn rocking mode at Ca.740 cm^{-1} . Methyl compounds of Group IV elements are usually characterised by the presence of a very strong band between 700-900 cm^{-1} which has been assigned to a methyl rocking mode³⁰. The band present in methyltin compounds at ~ 70 cm^{-1} may arise due to CH_3 -Sn rocking mode and in ethyl and other alkyltin compounds due to CH_2 -Sn. In diethyltin dichloride CH_2 -Sn and C-Me rocking modes occur at 688 and 723 cm^{-1} respectively in the solid state (Nujol mull), but in solution the weak higher frequency band is no longer observed and the Sn- CH_2 rock of dichloride and the dialkoxides²⁹ occur at 681 cm^{-1} . Dillard and Lawson³¹, however, have assigned the 680 cm^{-1} band of tetraethyltin to the CH_3 -C rock and in triethylmethyltin assigned bands at 670 cm^{-1} to CH_3 -C rock and the 728 cm^{-1} band to the CH_2 -rock. In 5,7-dichloro- and 5,7-dibromo-8-quinolinol chelates, however, the unequivocal assignment of this band to CH_2 -Sn rock becomes difficult, since C-Cl and C-Br absorptions are reported to occur at 750-700 cm^{-1} and at 700-650 cm^{-1} respectively³². In organotin(IV)

TABLE 1—THE ANALYTICAL DATA FOR ORGANOTIN (IV) SUBSTITUTED OXINATES

Compound	Crystallising solvent	M. P. (°C)	Yield (%)	Analyses (%) ^a			
				C	H	N	Sn
1. Tris (5,7-dichloro-8-quinolinolato) ethyltin (IV) ^o	Pet. ether (60-80°)	161-63	82.2	44.09 (44.24)	2.61 (2.19)	5.34 (5.39)	14.65 (15.15)
2. Tris (5,7-dibromo-8-quinolinolato) ethyltin (IV)	Methanol	178-80	96.5	32.14 (32.68)	2.36 (1.81)	3.63 (4.01)	11.01 (11.24)
3. Tris (5-nitro-8-quinolinolato) ethyltin (IV)	Benzene	>250 (decmp.)	66.6	49.47 (48.73)	3.98 (4.06)	11.26 (11.76)	16.16 (16.61)
4. Tris (5,7-dinitro-8-quinolinolato) ethyltin (IV)	DMF + water	229-30	25.59	41.30 (40.97)	3.01 (2.01)	14.33 (14.79)	14.43 (13.98)
5. Chlorobis (5,7-dichloro-8-quinolinolato) ethyltin (IV)	Pet. ether (60°-80°)	120-21	59.2	38.90 (39.41)	2.90 (2.15)	3.86 (4.61)	19.95 (19.48)
6. Chlorobis (5,7-dibromo-8-quinolinolato) ethyltin (IV)	Benzene	212-3	85	31.57 (30.50)	2.60 (2.08)	3.79 (3.56)	14.98 (15.08)
7. (5,7-Dibromo-8-quinolinolato) triethyltin (IV) ^o	Carbon tetrachloride	70-73	—	36.09 (35.48)	3.74 (3.69)	2.34 (2.76)	23.89 (23.93)
8. (5,7-Dibromo-8-quinolinolato) triphenyltin (IV)	Cyclohexane	176-8	70	50.18 (49.76)	3.55 (3.38)	2.86 (2.15)	18.12 (18.24)
9. (5,7-dichloro-8-quinolinolato) triphenyltin (IV)	Pet-ether (60°-80°)	123-24	80	56.98 (57.69)	3.68 (3.38)	2.34 (2.49)	20.32 (20.65)
10. (5-Nitro-8-quinolinolato) triphenyltin (IV)	„	162-64	74.3	59.63 (60.19)	3.95 (3.71)	6.19 (5.19)	21.93 (22.03)
11. (5,7-Dinitro-8-quinolinolato) triphenyltin (IV)	Methanol	235-6	—	55.55 (55.01)	3.11 (3.26)	7.70 (7.36)	20.65 (20.31)
12. (8-Mercapto-quinolinolato) triphenyltin (IV)	Benzene	167-68	—	63.93 (63.50)	4.34 (4.12)	2.42 (2.74)	23.17 (23.25)
13. (8-Quinolinolato) (1,3-diphenyl-propanedionato)-diethyltin (IV)	Pet. Ether (60-80°)	71-73	66.1	60.99 (61.66)	5.44 (4.97)	2.05 (2.50)	21.60 (21.83)
14. (8-Quinolinolato)(1-phenyl-1,3-butanedionato)-diethyltin (IV) ^b	Pet. ether or Alcohol	138-9°	—	57.58 (57.30)	4.92 (5.19)	2.8 (2.91)	24.42 (24.65)

a Calculated values are given in parentheses

b This compound was also prepared by refluxing bis (8-quinolinolato) diethyltin and benzoylacetone in alcohol for 5 hrs.

c The starting materials, (C₈H₆)₂SnCl and C₈H₆SnCl₂ were purified by fractional distillation
 Anal. found (C₈H₆)₂SnCl : Sn, 48.92 (49.21); Cl, 14.31 (14.73); for C₈H₆SnCl₂ : Sn, 47.12 (46.81); Cl, 41.46 (42.01 %).

TABLE 2—ULTRAVIOLET ABSORPTION SPECTRA OF 8-QUINOLINOLS

Compound	Solvent	λ_{max} (nm)	ϵ (M ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹) × 10 ⁻³
1. 8-Quinolinol ^a	CHCl ₃	320	2.70
2. 8-Quinolinol, 5,7-dichloro	CHCl ₃	337	3.00
3. 8-Quinolinol, 5,7-dibromo ^a	CHCl ₃	337	3.00
4. 8-Quinolinol, 5-nitro	Methanol	340	9.26
5. 8-Quinolinol, 5,7-dinitro	Dioxane	355	—
6. 8-Mercaptoquinoline	Methanol	340	1.37

^a λ_{max} for these compounds was reported.

TABLE 3—P. M. R. SPECTRAL DATA FOR THE MIXED CHELATES (SOLVENT : CARBONTETRACHLORIDE).

Compound	Ring protons (τ) (include =CH of the β -diketone)	Ethyl- (τ) protons
1. (C ₈ H ₆) ₂ Sn(Ox)- (C ₈ H ₆ COCHCOC ₈ H ₆)	1.5, 2.03 2.57, 2.93 3.15, 3.6	8.0 8.83
2. (C ₈ H ₆) ₂ Sn(Ox)- (C ₈ H ₆ COCHCOCH ₃)	1.57, 2.0 2.40, 2.58 3.00, 3.17	7.5 8.83

TABLE 4—ULTRAVIOLET ABSORPTION SPECTRA OF ORGANOTIN (IV) SUBSTITUTED OXINATES

Compound	Solvent	λ_{max} (nm.)	ϵ ($M^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) $\times 10^{-4}$
1. $(C_4H_9)_2Sn(Ox)_2$ ^{+*}	Benzene	385	6.19
2. $(C_8H_9)_2Sn(5,7\text{-dichloro-Ox})_2$	Methanol	390 343	6.49 5.90
3. $(C_8H_9)_2Sn(5,7\text{-dibromo-Ox})_2$	"	395 340	6.13 5.75
4. $(C_8H_9)_2Sn(5\text{-nitro-Ox})_2$	Methanol+dioxane	390 330	8.26 8.82
5. $(C_8H_9)_2Sn(5,7\text{-dinitro-Ox})_2$	dioxane	385 300	1.31 1.08
6. $(CH_3)_4SnCl(Ox)_2^*$	Benzene	383	4.07
7. $(C_8H_9)_2SnCl(5,7\text{-dichloro-Ox})_2$	Methanol	398 330	3.92 3.95
8. $(C_8H_9)_2SnCl(5,7\text{-dibromo-Ox})_2$	"	398 340	4.62 2.30
9. $(CH_3)_4Sn(Ox)_2$	Benzene	380	4.86
10. $(C_8H_9)_2Sn(Ox)_2$	Methanol	375	3.48
11. $(C_4H_9)_2Sn(Ox)_2$	"	375	7.8
12. $(C_8H_{17})_2Sn(Ox)_2$	"	375	29.63
13. $(C_8H_9)_2Sn(5,7\text{-dichloro-Ox})_2$	Methanol+CHCl ₃	390 340	6.95 6.02
14. $(C_8H_9)_2Sn(5,7\text{-dibromo-Ox})_2$	"	395 345	6.32 2.66
15. $(C_8H_9)_2Sn(5\text{-nitro-Ox})_2$	Methanol	410 320	4.27 1.18
16. $(CH_3)_4SnOx^*$	Cyclohexane	362	2.50
17. $(C_8H_9)_2Sn(5,7\text{-dibromo-Ox})_2$	"	390 350	2.92 2.42
	Methanol	400 330	3.92 3.95
18. $(C_8H_9)_2SnOx^*$	Cyclohexane	368	2.44
19. $(C_8H_9)_2Sn(5,7\text{-dichloro-Ox})_2$	"	385 340	3.93 2.31
20. $(C_8H_9)_2Sn(5,7\text{-dibromo-Ox})_2$	"	395 340	4.04 2.82
21. $(C_8H_9)_2Sn(5\text{-nitro-Ox})_2$	CHCl ₃	340	9.56
22. $(C_8H_9)_2Sn(8\text{-S-quinoline})_2$		360	—
23. $(C_8H_9)_2Sn(Ox)(DBM)$	Cyclohexane	~390, 337	—
24. $(C_8H_9)_2Sn(Ox)(BA)$		~390, 337	—

* λ_{max} for these compounds was reported†HO_X=8-quinolinol.

chelates of 5-nitro-8-quinolinol and 5,7-dinitro-8-quinolinol strong ligand absorption bands are found in this region ($750-770\text{ cm}^{-1}$).

The I. R. spectra of triphenyltin(IV) substituted-8-quinolinols show a strong absorption band at $1070-80\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Henry and Noites³³ and Poller³⁴ have shown that the band at 1065 cm^{-1} , in compounds of the general type, $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{SnA}_{4-x}$ (X =a diversity of chemical types) is characteristic of the phenyltin group and has a diagnostic value. This band has also been noted by a number of other workers and assigned to a C-H in plane deformation vibration³⁵.

The strong broad band observed at $\text{Ca.}450\text{ cm}^{-1}$, in the spectra of organotin(IV) substituted-oxinates has been assigned to tin-oxygen stretching vibration on the basis of corresponding assignments in organotin-8-quinolinolates¹. The other new band observed at $\text{Ca.}370\text{ cm}^{-1}$ has been assigned to $\nu(\text{Sn-N})$ modes³⁶. The Sn-C stretching frequency is observed as a strong band in the spectra of all the mono- and tri-substituted oxinates in the region $560-580\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Mixed chelates: The proton chemical shifts of the compounds (8-quinolinolato) (1-phenyl-1,3-butanedionato)diethyltin(IV) and (8-quinolinolato)(1,3-diphenylpropanedionato)-diethyltin(IV) given in Table 3 are comparable with the corresponding shifts in the diphenyltin mixed chelates, $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{Sn}(\text{Ox})$ ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COCHCO}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$) reported by Westlake and Martin³⁷. The observed intensity ratios of ethyl and ring protons (include=CH of the β -diketone) agree fairly well with the calculated values (2:3 and 2:3.4) in $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{Sn}(\text{Ox})(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COCHCOCH}_3)$ and in $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{Sn}(\text{Ox})(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{COCHCOCH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)$, respectively. In the I. R. spectra of the mixed chelates $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{Sn}(\text{Ox})(\text{DBM})$ and $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{Sn}(\text{Ox})(\text{BA})$ a medium intense peak is observed at $\sim 1230\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which can be ascribed to a CH in-plane bending vibration in analogy with the reported³⁸ CH in plane bending frequency in copper and nickel chelates of dibenzoylmethane and benzoylacetone. The band observed at $\text{Ca.}1500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of these organotin(IV) mixed chelates can be assigned to the phenyl ring vibrations. The asymmetric CH_2 -deformation of Sn-Et, a characteristic band of Sn-alkyl groups³⁹ could be located at 1450 cm^{-1} . The new frequency observed in these chelates at 750 cm^{-1} is due to the Sn- CH_2 rocking mode³⁰.

In the mass spectra of organotin(IV) mixed chelates, fragmentation path-ways corresponding to the presence of both the ligands are observed. In the spectrum of $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{Sn}(\text{Ox})(\text{BA})$, only a weak molecular ion is observed at $m/e\ 484$. Successive losses of ethyl radicals from the parent ion result in the formation of the low valent species SnL_1L_2 ($m/e\ 425$) (where $\text{L}_1=\text{Ox}$ and $\text{L}_2=\text{BA}$). Another mode of fragmentation of the molecular ion appears to be the loss of a methyl radical followed by the elimination of ethylene ($m/e\ 441$). The appearance of a peak at $m/e\ 158$ according to the

scheme reported earlier¹⁰ confirms this mode of dissociation. Although the molecular ion is not observed in the spectrum of $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{Sn}(\text{Ox})(\text{DBM})$, loss of a methyl radical followed by ethylene elimination can be observed at $m/e\ 502$. A weak peak observed at $m/e\ 158$ supports this mode of disintegration. The other low valent species, SnL_1^+ , SnL_2^+ (in abundance), $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{SnL}_1$ and fragment ions corresponding to 8-quinolinol and β -diketones³⁰ are also observed in the spectra of both the mixed chelates.

Acknowledgement

One of us (Miss C.D.B.) thanks the C.S.I.R. for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship.

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